

DIVINFOOD

**Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains
to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food**

Deliverable D6.3

***Roadmaps to organise
on-field training workshops
and demonstration days***

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Table of content

- SUMMARY 4**
 - OBJECTIVES.....4
 - RATIONALE.....4
 - TEAMS INVOLVED4
- INTRODUCTION 5**
- 1. ROADMAPS..... 6**
 - 1.1 PLANNING A WORKSHOP OR A DEMONSTRATION6
 - It starts with an idea and brainstorming 6*
 - Timeline and social context..... 7*
 - Location supporting structures and material 8*
 - Costs and budget10*
 - Invitation and announcement.....10*
 - Develop a programme11*
 - Logistics of the event.....13*
 - Communication.....13*
 - 1.2 ONE TO TWO WEEKS BEFORE THE WORKSHOP 13
 - 1.3 THE DAY OF THE WORKSHOP..... 14
 - 1.4 END/AFTER THE OFFICIAL PROGRAMME 14
- 2. ORGANISING TRAINING AND DEMONSTRATION IN DIVINFOOD..... 15**
- 3. CONCLUSION 16**

Table of pictures

- Image 1 : 7
- Image 2 : 9
- Image 3 : 10
- Image 4 : 12
- Image 5 : 13
- Image 6 : 13

Summary

Objectives

The objective of this D6.3 deliverable is to provide a generic and pragmatic route towards the organization of on-field training workshops and demonstration days. The roadmap can be used for planning both on-field training and demonstration days for food consumers, farmers, and boards of directors across the country, and it can be used when different aspects are brought into focus, e.g., growing food crops and preparing food. Roadmaps considered in this report include elements such as timeline, social context, location, organisation of a programme, announcement, and communication. Finally, there is also mention of aspects to consider one to two weeks before the event, at the event and after the official programme is announced. The roadmap will be illustrated by examples and pictures from different types of events held in Denmark by Innovation Centre for Organic Farming. The roadmaps are applicable in European countries, depending on structures in the given country, e.g., the relation between the farmers, advisory services, and different stakeholders.

Rationale

As the roadmap is targeting a pragmatic approach it is described using different examples and experiences from real on-field events held in Denmark. The events range from one-hour field meetings that gather participants from the local area on short notice to large-scale all-day events for up to 500 participants involving many stakeholders. This range was chosen to demonstrate that careful planning is essential, the extent of which will depend on the number of participants, stakeholders involved and the duration of the event.

Teams involved

Draft and text made by DIVINFOOD partner Innovation Centre for Organic Farming (ICOEL) with input from Danish Vegetarian Society (DVF) and Open Food France (OFFr). Reviews by partners OFFr, INRAE and IT.

Introduction

On-field training provides great opportunities to demonstrate how particular practices are carried out and to let people interact and be curious in relation to certain subjects. Workshops and demonstration days are some specific examples of such. A training workshop is described as a meeting dedicated to understanding processes, mechanisms and often with less participants than a demonstration. A demonstration event can be seen as more open, lighter, and focused on results with explanation of how something works or is performed. Training workshops may involve a practical session in which participants practise something, while in demonstration days, they only see, adopting a more passive attitude. The DIVINFOOD project develops a participatory approach, which is especially relevant in relation to training workshops, meaning that trainers can be for example farmers or cooks themselves, to value their knowledge and promote peer-training. In relation to organisation, there are many overlaps between the two, training workshop and demonstration days: the roadmaps described in this report are applicable for both types of events.

Since the DIVINFOOD project considers short and mid-tier food chains, the focal points of this document will be the food value chain from farmer to consumer and stakeholders related to this. A successful event is preceded by hours of planning. This brief report presents roadmaps containing detailed plans to guide the progress towards executing successful events and describes useful aspects to take into consideration before, during and after the event. On-field training days and demonstrations can range from a quick trip to the field with local farmers to large-scale national events with several hundreds of participants involved. In the following, examples are provided of different events in different formats for a varied number of participants, held in Denmark.

1. Roadmaps

1.1 Planning a workshop or a demonstration

The planning process before the event is often the most time-consuming part of the process, and the steps presented in the roadmaps can be approached in different order. Perhaps the date has been set before the location is decided or vice versa, but nevertheless, it is recommended, all steps are considered before the event.

It starts with an idea and brainstorming

On-field training starts with a desire to get out of the purely theoretical field and see how particular activities are carried out in practice. In relation to the objective of DIVINFOOD to co-organise training workshops and demonstration days, this brainstorming phase should preferably be done with stakeholders and local actors. The co-organisation provides great perspectives and inputs to the event and connected activities.

In the beginning it may be useful to ask some key questions. Note that answering the questions in this order is not relevant:

- *What is the aim of the workshop/demonstration?*
- *What do we want to demonstrate?*
- *What do we want participants to know more about after the event?*
- *Do we want to create new relations between stakeholders?*

In relation to asking these questions, brainstorm on who the relevant stakeholders and/or participants are:

- *Is the event relevant to farmers, breeders, processors, chefs or other kitchen professionals, retailers, consumers or to the whole value chain?*
- *What is the purpose and target group of the event? How should e.g., field trials be developed so that relevant target groups can have them demonstrated?*
- *Are there any synergies to other activities?*
- *Are any stakeholders willing to contribute to the event e.g., by demonstrating equipment or sponsoring some of the costs?*

Example: thematic days gathering value chain actors

An event with demonstration and tastings on-field was organised in Denmark. The main target group members were farmers and the visit included a field visit to look at crops and trials. However, the event also included a demonstration of various drying equipment, a tasting of different types of lentils, peas, chickpeas, and fava beans grown in Denmark and a presentation of sensory profiling. Indeed, to make participants in a value chain aware of the entire chain and improve their understanding of partners' opportunities and challenges in the value chain, it is necessary to bring people together. This is of high relevance for the DIVINFOOD project. Often, meetings for consumers and companies take place in meeting rooms but meetings can successfully be arranged at farms, involving chefs to prepare lunch and breeders to demonstrate, for instance.

Image 1: An example on a demonstration of grain legumes being produced for food. Photos: Inger Bertelsen, Innovation Centre for Organic Farming

Timeline and social context

In the planning process, it is important to make a detailed plan for the event which must also be realistic. If the schedule is too tight, there is no buffer for any unpredictable situations that may arise. This may result in additional time pressure, and the quality of the event may be impaired. Depending on the scale of the event, the planning process can start from a few weeks before the event takes place to even years before the date of the event. If a winter-sown crop is to be demonstrated in the summer, planning must start already in autumn. If a machine is to be demonstrated in the field, the machine manufacturer should be involved in the planning process so that a crop is in the right development stage and in good condition for demonstration machine performance. If freshly harvested crops are to be demonstrated to chefs and other kitchen professionals, the event should preferably take place in the harvest season. It is necessary to start planning years in advance when for instance crops are to be demonstrated as they must be sown and grown in due time before the demonstration. Furthermore, an analysis should be made of the context and surrounding society to investigate for instance whether there are any public holidays, busy periods for farmers or any other relevant parameters that can affect the anticipated number of attendants or the subject that is to be demonstrated.

Example: Machine demonstration of e.g., row hoeing

In this case, the right conditions, including weather conditions are necessary to carry out a successful demonstration. The equipment is widely used, and most farmers are not willing to drive far for this type of demonstration. Announcements are made shortly before the event via social media and e-mails to communicate quickly. The duration of the event is approximately one hour.

Example: Field visits in on-farm trials

In Denmark, national field trials are conducted all over the country in farmers' fields. Often, field trials are situated close to each other, and it is then possible to visit several field trials the same day. Normally the duration is half a day.

Further information including the location of all national field trials in 2022 is accessible online at [Nordic Field Trial System - Oversight \(dlbr.dk\)](https://nfts.dlbr.dk)

Image 2: Field trials in Denmark, Nordic Field Trial Systems (source: nfts.dlbr.dk).

Location supporting structures and material

Choosing the right location for the on-field demonstration or workshop is very important and relates to questions such as: what is to be demonstrated and depending on what is to be demonstrated, you might need a larger stage.

- *Who are the members of the target group, and who should be (or needs to be) invited?*
- *Consider how many participants are expected to attend.*
- *Is the goal to attract participants from the local area or to attract as many participants as possible which means infrastructure is important to take into consideration so that the chosen location is close to, e.g.: a highway.*
- *Are speakers and microphones necessary and available?*

- *Is payment expected for renting the location or for paying the farmer for allowing access to a field for instance?*

Location setting is also very relevant if the members of the target group are based in different countries, or participants are coming from far away. To decide where the best place for the event is, take into consideration transportation and parking options as well as accommodation offers in the area, considering the budget for the event. Are activities planned inside and outside or both? If the event is taking place at more than one location it is advisable to find out how long it takes for the participants to go from A to B, which should be included in the programme. At large-scale events involving a great number of people, in the range of 100-500, such aspects as fire regulations or notification to local authorities can be relevant. Practical issues such as toilet facilities, waste disposal and even first aid resources (equipment and personnel) must be considered.

Example: Large-scale national demonstration days

Planning large-scale events takes time and effort but also provides unique opportunities to reach a big audience. In Denmark, a yearly event is “Grovfoderekskursionen” which facilitates visits to two dairy farms, demonstrating crops, machinery, stables, economy e.g., that are currently relevant to dairy farmers. Up to 900 participants attend. In Sweden, a yearly called “Borgeby fältdagar” with different themes every year attracts even more participants. In 2022, the first National Organic Field Day took place in Denmark, see Image 3. At such large events it is necessary to consult the local authorities and consider aspects such as fire exits, power supply and toilet facilities. The event took place at Funen, Denmark, as this location is in the middle of the country and is easier for participants to reach in reasonable time for a one-day visit. Meanwhile it was placed close to highways and hotels for overnight stays. It is highly relevant for a project such as DIVIN FOOD to participate at events like these.

Image 3: National Organic Field Day 2022. Photo: Lars Egelund Olsen, Innovation Centre for Organic Farming.

Costs and budget

Costs and budget are of course a crucial part of planning a workshop or demonstration. There are different ways to fund workshops, demonstrations, and training activities. Consider funding such as the EU leader programme or other projects sharing similar activities that can cover some of the costs. Sometimes companies will contribute with resources in connection to machine or seed and plant demonstrations. If the organisers do not have enough funds, they might need to ask for additional support from participants. There are other items to take in consideration in respect to costs:

- *Will you be funded to organise this event?*
- *Should you ask additional resources to your stakeholders?*

If you are inviting people to participate in the event, consider costs associated to this. Even if they do not receive fees for their participation, you should still consider if you need to support their travel costs, meal costs and even accommodation costs. Note that clarification on costs and budget is preferably one of the first considerations which should be done before sending invitations.

Invitation and announcement

When the purpose of the event is clarified, the location chosen and target group identified, it is time to send out invitations. Also consider people who are not part of the target group or participating in the event as such but need to be invited anyway. For example, if you are using a facility from the municipality, maybe a municipality representative should be invited; if you are receiving funding from a Foundation maybe you should invite a representative of this foundation or if your project has an advisory group, you should probably invite a representative too. Set a date for the event and a “pre” date for RSVP’s. Consider how participants should sign up, e.g., via email or an online registration form. At the same time, decide how to register the participants at the workshop. There are different digital tools, which facilitate the handling of registrations and payments.

- *Will it be necessary to have a ticket?*
- *Is it an open event so that participants do not need to sign up?*
- *Does it cost anything to participate or is it free?*
- *Will there be a no-show fee?*

Consider also how to reach the relevant stakeholders via potential channels, e.g., social media platforms, advertisement in newspapers or personal invitation.

Example: DIVINFOOD workshop via personal invitation

In the first year of the DIVINFOOD project a workshop was organised by the Faba-Nord and Leg-Nord Living Labs. The focus was to encourage stakeholders related to the grain legume value chain to meet each other. The target group were people that were already active in the value chain for one or more of the considered crops, therefore it was chosen to make personal invitations. An invitation letter was sent by email and followed up by a personal phone call. This approach was made because a very specific group of participants was crucial to make the workshop a success and important for the development of further actions for the living lab. The invitation was made both in Danish, Swedish and English, depending on the receiver.

Agro Food Park d. 09.01.2023

Invitation to DIVINFOOD Living Lab workshop

Friday 13. January 2023 10.30 – 15.00, room B660, 6th floor
Location: Copenhagen Hospitality College, Vigerslev Allé 18, 2500 Valby.

The first meeting in the Living Lab on Lentil, grey pea and lupin and the Living Lab on faba beans will be held together in Copenhagen. Participants invited to the Living Labs are already active in the value chain for one or more of these crops. The meeting will be the starting point on working together to make these grain legumes successful as food. The DIVINFOOD project gives us opportunity to work cross border and share knowledge and solutions and tackle obstacles. Link to the project's homepage: [DIVINFOOD – AgrobioDiversity IN healthy plant-based FOOD](#).

Agenda

10.30 Welcome to the meeting and the Copenhagen Hospitality College (coffee/bread)
Inger Bertelsen Innovation Centre for Organic Farming and Michelle Werther, Copenhagen Hospitality College

Living Labs and DIVINFOOD /Inger Bertelsen
Welcome and presentation of DIVINFOOD project

- Project needs from the Living Labs
- Your output from the project
- Shaping the Living Labs

Participant presentation

State of the art in Sweden and Denmark
- Lentils, grey peas, narrow leaved lupins and faba beans /Georg Carlsson, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, and Inger Bertelsen

12.15 Lunch with grain legumes prepared by Copenhagen Hospitality College (in the canteen area)

13.15 Workshop
How can the Living Labs contribute to an increased production and use of lentil, grey peas, lupins and faba beans for food? What should be the goal?
What can we learn from a Swedish – Danish Living Lab?
How can you contribute and what can you get out of participating?
Which activities do we want to set up in the Living Lab during the project period? How do we want to organize these activities.

Best regards

SLU, Dansk Vegetarisk Forening, Nordisk Råvara og Innovationscenter for Økologisk Landbrug

Image 4: Example of an invitation letter containing information about the purpose of the workshop and with a program of the day. The invitation was followed by a personal telephone call.

Develop a programme

When developing a programme for the event, the initial question should be:

- *What do we want to demonstrate and once again who are the members of the target group?*

Make a draft for a realistic programme, considering realistic timeslots to allow breaks; meals; and transportation. Incorporate time-points into the programme. If stakeholders are invited to give presentations or do practical demonstrations at the event, make sure they are informed about the fact that they appear in the programme, understand their role, and have been given relevant information about the audience. If meals, beverages, and snacks are to be served at the event, make proper arrangements. For events related to DIVINFOOD, promote legumes- and minor cereal-based minimal processed and local products and recipes, in line with the project's objectives. When the programme is developed, share it with the participants to ensure they know what to expect from participating at the demonstration or workshop. Make either a simple or a detailed programme with time indications, depending on your target group and relevance.

Example: Signs in field trials and time for discussion

Here a group of farmers and advisors met to look at field trials, see Image 5. Participants were enabled to explore their own fields. Allow sufficient time for discussion. Image 6 is an example on how to make the trials easily accessible by making a path in the field.

Image 5: Signs in the field trials. Photo: Inger Bertelsen, Innovation Centre for Organic Farming.

Image 6: Explaining and showing field trials with faba beans in Denmark. Photo: Inger Bertelsen, Innovation Centre for Organic Farming.

Logistics of the event

Managing a program involves organizing the logistics of the event. This integrates logistics like ordering food from caterers with references, asking if participants and presenters have diet restrictions, ordering enough food for each meal break and notify when a meal will be supplied in the event. For example, if the event ends late and you will not cover dinner or maybe it ends early but you would still like people to stay and visit the location and should be back for dinner. Provide an estimate for the food provider or caterer of the number of participants and agree when the exact number is provided. In DIVINFOOD, promote local small-scale food caterers (it could be farmers who diversified their activities). Practical matters include making sure the following is provided and taken care of tables, chairs, cutlery, toilets, logistics, cooling storage etc. If help is needed for some tasks, make sure the right staff (and/or volunteers) will be there to take care of the tasks.

Communication

The choice of language must be carefully considered when communicating the event. This is especially important when planning events across borders for people based in different countries. Consider if there is a common language but also consider what the stakeholders prefer. Aspects related to communication during the workshop, or the demonstration must also be considered. Maybe a translator is necessary if languages are very different. Keep in mind who is the target group and how should we communicate to them. Communication also requires ensuring that all the organisations which have in some way contributed to the event are credited. For example, ensuring the right logos are on all media used.

Example: Living Labs between Denmark and Sweden

For example, as a part of the DIVINFOOD project, the two living labs Leg-Nord and Faba-Nord held a workshop in Copenhagen (DK) where stakeholders from Sweden and Denmark were invited. The invited farmers preferred to speak Danish and Swedish to each other, whereas other stakeholders preferred communicating in English. The solution in that situation was to make invitation letters and written information in English, Danish and Swedish, and at the workshop, participants spoke all three languages.

1.2 One to two weeks before the workshop

All the above-mentioned steps of the roadmap are important considerations to reflect on early in the process. It is recommended to have a look at the plans and agreements one to two weeks prior to the event and make sure all practicalities are taken care of. Visit the host or the field to prepare for the event and have a look at the location if possible. If not, call someone who is there and knows e.g., how the crop is performing and if everything that is to be demonstrated at the event is visible and ready. Check up on the practical aspects:

- *Is everything still OK with the speakers?*
- *Is everything OK with caring for the participants arrival and stay?*

- *Is the logistical material ordered and reserved for the workshop on a good route?*
- *If you are asking for extra staff or volunteers, are they still aware of their commitment?*
- *Are all the Health and Safety aspects confirmed?*

Inform the host/farmer at the location how many participants are coming, share the time schedule, expectations etc. If meals, beverages, and snacks are to be served, inform the relevant people the exact number of participants and make proper arrangements: Are meals and beverages delivered or picked up – and when? Is it necessary to make sure cold storage is possible? How is the weather forecast for the date of the event? Consider if it is necessary to produce and set up signs at the location and if it will be relevant for the participants to wear name tags. It is also advised to send out a reminder for the people who signed up for the event. Make a final effort to guarantee everyone who is interested in the theme of the event has been notified that it is taking place. For example, farmers have a busy and weather-dependent schedule and often sign-up last minute.

1.3 The day of the workshop

On the day of the event, many hours of planning are finally realized. At this point, the plans will be actualized, and it is time to let the participants contribute to achieving the goal of a successful day by showing up and showing commitment to the event and its activities.

On the demonstration or workshop day, show up early. At large-scale events, arriving the day before is crucial. Imagine being a participant at the workshop who does not know the place or where to go. Are signs, fences and/or people needed to guide participant and let them know where to go? Greet participants when they arrive. If participants are to be registered when they arrive, make sure time allows. Welcome the participants officially, present relevant organizers, set the scene, remind the participants what is on the agenda for the event and tell them what to expect as well as some housekeeping rules, e.g.: where is the fire exists; where they can find toilets; where they shall have a coffee break or other meals; etc. Thank the host and allow him- or herself time to introduce their work as well as the location. Bear in mind all participants (potentially some of the speakers) are there as guests. Make sure a coordinator is present for the duration of the event to be one step ahead of the programme and arrange the next item on the agenda, making the participants and speakers feel the event is well organised and proceeding smoothly.

1.4 End/after the official programme

When the event is completed successfully, let all participants know that the workshop/demonstration has ended and thank them for showing up. Acknowledge the host/farmer and/or other stakeholders who have contributed at the event. If relevant provide further relevant information for the participants, e.g., about the theme of the event or similar events. The organiser or a representative from the organisation should preferably stay until all

participants have left. Be there to answer questions if there are any. Thank the host or the owner of the location. Evaluate the event together and ask the host /owner to share observations. Make sure that the location is tidy before leaving. After the event consider aspects such as:

- *Are there notes to be written and who is responsible for writing them?*
- *Are there any papers or presentation to be shared with the audience, for example send by email or other platforms they use?*
- *Are there videos to be uploaded so that the event can be seen by those who could not be present?*
- *Is there a promotion that should be done on social media with short posts of achieved outcomes and even some unexpected and positive developments accompanied by photos that demonstrate key moments of the event?*
- *Is there a short text you can write for a local newspaper/for your newsletter or for the newsletter of your stakeholders?*

These post communications considerations could support the profile of the organisers, the participants and the DIVINFOOD project as a whole.

2. Organising training and demonstration in DIVINFOOD

There we shortly summarize what is needed when partners organize an on-field training workshop or a demonstration day in the DIVINFOOD project, in line with what was planned in the Description of Action (DoA):

- *At least 45 on-field demonstration days or hands-on training events are planned to disseminate key results and tools targeting farmers, breeders, small-scale processors, chefs, students (1 pr. year pr. Living Lab). Cross-visits between LLs will be facilitated, some in relation with project's annual meetings.*
- *Events must value and/or feed LL results, then mobilize DIVINFOOD partners*
- *Participants should be registered on a sign-in sheet with DIVINFOOD and EU logos*
- *Events have to be documented in the monitoring tool, in which the type of results which will be valued and/or fed through the event should be highlighted:*
<https://sites.inra.fr/site/divinfood/SitePages/Living%20Labs%20welcome%20page.aspx>
- *Participants should be characterised with few questions, to evaluate the project's capacity to reach a diversity of people (age group, job, locality, etc.).*

3. Conclusion

The report addresses and provides roadmaps for issues that must be considered before, during and after on-field training workshops and demonstration days, especially applicable for events in relation to food value chains. A great part of carrying out on-field training is the preparation stage, which is time consuming but necessary to execute a successful event. Some of the main questions to ask are, what is the theme of the workshop/demonstration, what should be demonstrated, what should participants know after the event? These questions should be kept in mind throughout the process of planning and executing the event. Roadmaps presented in this report include aspects such as timeline, social context, costs and budget, logistics, location, organisation of a programme, communication, and announcement. Further, aspects to consider one to two weeks before the event, at the event and after the event are described. The steps of the roadmaps are illustrated with some specific examples and images from different types of events held in Denmark: machine demonstration, field visits to on-farm trials, thematic days gathering value chain actors and last, but not least, large-scale national demonstration days.

DIVINFOOD

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to value agrobioDiversity IN healthy plant-based FOOD

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